

Finnish anthropogenic habitat types and assessment of their ecological condition

JOEL JALKANEN, OLIVIA MAHLIO, EINI NIEMINEN, TUULI KASSI, EMMA LUOMA, JOHANNA HUTTUNEN, JOHANNA TUOMISAARI, ANNA PURSIAINEN, PANU HALME, HEIDI AHLGREN, ANTTI HANNULA, ELISA LÄHDE

This is a direct translation of the original Finnish-language report:

<https://figbc.fi/julkaisut/rakennetun-ympariston-luontotyytit-ja-niiden-ekologisen-tilan-arviointi>

Authors:

Joel Jalkanen¹, Olivia Mahlio², Eini Nieminen³, Tuuli Kassi², Emma Luoma⁴, Johanna Huttunen⁵,
Johanna Tuomisaari³, Anna Pursiainen⁶, Panu Halme^{3,7}, Heidi Ahlgren⁶, Antti Hannula⁸,
Merete Kemppainen² and Elisa Lähde²

¹Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki

²Aalto University

³University of Jyväskylä & JYU. Wisdom – School of Resource Wisdom

⁴Akordi Ltd

⁵City of Vantaa

⁶City of Espoo

⁷Finnish Environment Institute

⁸City of Helsinki

Cover illustration:

City of Helsinki / Nea Vesterinen and Sara Korkeamäki.

The project has received funding from the Strategic Research Council (grants #364448, #364450, #364453; BOOST project) and the European Regional Development Fund.

Content

Forested parks	2
Gardens	6
Ground-contact yards	10
Shrub vegetation	14
Open parks	17
Novel meadows	20
Ruderal areas	24
Fields	27
Road- and railside vegetation	30
Vegetation of streets and squares	33
Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures	36
Habitats created through industrial processes	39
Artificial wetlands	42
Artificial shores	45
Artificial water basins	48
Artificial ponds and running waters	52
References	54

Forested parks

Description of habitat type

Forested parks are forested or semi-open public or semi-public spaces growing trees with average heights of over 5 metres and a canopy coverage of at least 10%. The canopy coverage also includes naturally short tree species, such as cherries, even if they do not fulfil the 5-metre canopy height criteria. As a distinction from forested squares (see Vegetation of streets and squares), the ground surface is unpaved except for walking paths. This habitat type also includes areas that do not quite fit the criteria of tree height and/or canopy coverage due to young age but that can be assumed, over time and considering the usage and maintenance of these areas, to fulfil these criteria at a later time.

This habitat type is broad and includes various green spaces. It incorporates artificial parks, cemeteries, manor parks, and other similar green spaces. However, nurseries, orchards, or allotment gardens with cottages (see Gardens) are not included.

Forested parks also include woodlands that have originated in green spaces, on idle land, or in other built areas but that cannot be considered natural forest types. The division between forested parks in built environments and human-influenced natural forest types may be vague. Natural forest types are spaces where natural forest vegetation is dominant, and seedling sprouting is natural. Forested parks are spaces that have formed in human-modified or human-founded areas and that, based on their vegetation, are not considered herb-rich forests, heath forests, or other natural forest types. Abandoned, naturally forested fields are classified as a natural forest type despite their field origin remaining a recognizable aspect.

The trees and vegetation of this habitat type vary considerably depending on the foundation or creation method and management. The trees can either spread naturally and be unmanaged, or they can be planted and managed. Similarly, the vegetation varies from intensively managed lawns to versatile plantings, meadow-like areas, and spontaneously spread unmanaged vegetation. However, the vegetation community or structure does not resemble the vegetation of natural forest types, and the site's use and/or management do not allow the site to develop into a natural forest type.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, forested parks have versatile and varying trees and vegetation. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plant species and no invasive plants. Plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants and trees are adapted to their living habitat and are viable. Canopy coverage ranges from 30% to 70%, and the site has microclimatically variable areas. The vegetation is clearly stratified into four layers. The trees are Finnish or European in species and origin, of multiple species, and of various ages. The site also has old trees. Dead wood is abundant, and it varies in terms of diameter, position, microclimate, species community, and especially decay stage. The trees have holes and/or cavities that create microhabitats. The site can also have piles of rocks or other materials, which offer shelter for animals. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

In the best scenario, these lush, multilayered, and diverse forested parks offer habitats to a multitude of species. Old park trees offer habitats to various epiphytic mosses and lichen, to wood-decay and mycorrhiza fungi, and to invertebrates. Versatile dead wood communities support a diverse wood-decay community. Old and decayed hardwood trees, in particular, have a myriad of notable species typical for built environments. Dense, multilayered vegetation offers protection and nesting habitats for birds, mammals, and invertebrates.

Assessment tables for condition: Forested parks

	Vegetation:	Forest structure	Canopy coverage	Vegetation stratification	Quantity and structural attributes of dead wood, and piles of rocks or other materials and bird boxes:
	<p>1) multispecied,</p> <p>2) native Finnish and/or European community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte community,</p> <p>3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants,</p> <p>4) flowering is continuous from early to late summer</p>				<p>1) dead wood continuum</p> <p>2) downed and standing dead wood</p> <p>3) tree holes and cavities</p> <p>4) variable microclimate of dead wood</p> <p>5) dead wood comprises multiple species</p> <p><i>Large-diameter dead wood: basal diameter ≥ 30 cm.</i></p> <p><i>Small-diameter dead wood: basal diameter 5–<30 cm.</i></p>
1	<p>At least four attributes present.</p> <p>No invasive alien plant species present.</p>	<p>Tree community is uneven aged, and some trees are old according to species-specific standards.</p> <p>Tree community has multiple species.</p> <p>Most tree species are of Finnish or European origin.</p>	30–70%	Multilayered vegetation, four layers.	<p>Marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³ in total) of large-diameter dead wood and at least four structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, at least ca. 1 m³/ha of small-diameter dead wood present.</p>
0.9					<p>Marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³ in total) of large-diameter dead wood and at least three structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, at least ca. 1 m³/ha of small-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials (ca. 10 m³/ha, at least 1 m³ in total) or at least 10 bird boxes of three different types per hectare (at least 10 in total).</p>
0.8	Three attributes.	As condition class 1, but tree community is mostly of non-European origin.		Three layers.	
0.7					
0.6	<p>Two attributes present.</p> <p>Single invasive alien plant species may be present.</p>	<p>Tree community is mostly of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Tree community is either:</p> <p>a) even-aged, of a single species, and middle-aged but not old, or</p> <p>b) multispecied and comprises both young and middle-aged trees.</p>	>70%		<p>Dead wood is either:</p> <p>a) large-diameter dead wood in marked quantities and two large-diameter dead wood structural attributes present,</p> <p>b) large-diameter dead wood to some extent (ca. 2–<5 m³/ha, at least 2 m³) and four large-diameter dead wood structural attributes present, or</p> <p>c) small-diameter dead wood in marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) and four dead wood structural attributes present.</p> <p>Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) or at least 5 bird boxes of at least two different types (at least 5 in total).</p>
0.5				Two layers.	As condition class 0.6, but no piles of rocks or other materials and no bird boxes.

0.4	As condition class 0.6, but site has several occurrences of invasive alien plant species.	Tree community is mostly of Finnish or European origin. Tree community is either: a) even-aged, of a single species, and middle-aged but not old, or b) young but multispecied.	20– <30%		Large-diameter dead wood is present to a degree, and large-diameter dead wood shows clear variation in one or minor variation in at least two structural attributes.
0.3	One attribute present.				Either: a) small quantities of large-diameter dead wood or individual large-diameter dead wood objects, dead wood shows clear variation in one or slight variation in at least two structural attributes; no piles of rocks or other materials or bird boxes, or b) small quantities of large-diameter dead wood or individual large-diameter dead wood objects, dead wood does not exhibit variation in a single structural attribute, but site has marked piles of rocks or other materials or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare (at least 5 in total).
0.2					Either: a) dead wood is scarce or only occurs as individual object and dead wood does not exhibit variation in a single structural attribute, or b) no dead wood is present, but site has marked piles of rocks or other materials or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare (at least 5 in total).
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	Tree community consists of even-aged young individuals of one non-European tree species.	10– <20%	One layer present.	No dead wood, piles of rocks or other materials, or bird boxes present.
0	Not a habitat type				

Picture 1. Despite its name, the Helsinki Winter Garden is actually a forested park. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 2. Cemeteries are typically forested parks in Finland. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 3. Mustila Arboretum. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 4. Forested park at the spa hotel in Hanko. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Gardens

Description of habitat type

Gardens are public or private spaces reserved for growing useful and ornamental plants. This habitat type contains vegetable gardens, allotment gardens, and other similar open spaces. Allotment gardens with cottages, orchards, and nurseries are also included in this habitat type. Allotment gardens with and without cottages are public recreational areas; however, the actual allotment plots and cottages are nonetheless reserved for private use by the cultivators. This habitat type does not include small kitchen gardens in private yards (see Ground-contact yards) or planter boxes (see Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures).

Gardens are maintained and used for cultivating useful plants. Garden vegetation therefore mainly consists of ornamental and/or useful plants and weeds. Allotment gardens with and without cottages are usually cultivated and maintained according to rules set by the supervising organization.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, garden vegetation is versatile and variable. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. Useful plants are abundant, and/or the site also has other vegetation. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plant species and no invasive plant species. Plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants are adapted to their living habitat and are viable. The vegetation is clearly stratified into three layers (four layers for forested gardens). Dead wood is abundant, and it varies in terms of diameter, position, microclimate, species community, and especially decay stage. Trees have holes and/or cavities that create microhabitats. The site can also have piles of rocks or other materials, which offer shelter for animals. The trees in forested gardens are also Finnish or European in species and origin, of multiple species, and of various ages. The site also has old trees. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

In the best scenario, lush, multilayered, and diverse gardens support a diverse species composition. Flowering useful plants offer plentiful nutrition for pollinators. Abundant dead wood also supports pollinators in addition to a diverse wood-decay community. Rock walls and piles plus compost, leaf, and other heaps offer shelter and habitats for invertebrates. Dense, multilayered vegetation offers shelter and nesting places for birds, mammals, and invertebrates. Old trees offer habitats for various epiphytic mosses and lichen, wood-decay and mycorrhiza fungi, and invertebrates. The soil microbiota of gardens is diverse and viable at its best.

Assessment tables for condition: Gardens

	Vegetation:	Vegetation stratification	Quantity and structural attributes of dead wood, and piles of rocks or other materials and bird boxes:	Forest structure – only for forested sites
	<p>1) multispecied,</p> <p>2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species,</p> <p>3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants of animals,</p> <p>4) flowering is continuous from early to late summer</p>		<p>1) dead wood continuum</p> <p>2) downed and standing dead wood</p> <p>3) tree holes and cavities</p> <p>4) variable microclimate of dead wood</p> <p>5) dead wood comprises multiple species</p> <p><i>Large-diameter dead wood: basal diameter ≥ 30 cm.</i></p> <p><i>Small-diameter dead wood: basal diameter $5 < 30$ cm.</i></p>	
1	<p>Four attributes present.</p> <p>No invasive alien plant species present.</p>	<p>Multilayered vegetation.</p> <p>Forested gardens: four layers.</p> <p>Open gardens: three layers.</p>	<p>Marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) of large-diameter dead wood and at least four structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, at least ca. 1 m³/ha of small-diameter dead wood.</p>	<p>Tree community is uneven-aged and some trees are old according to species-specific standards.</p> <p>Tree community has multiple species.</p> <p>Most tree species are of Finnish or European origin.</p>
0.9			<p>Marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) of large-diameter dead wood and three structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, at least ca. 1 m³/ha of small-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials (ca. 10 m³/ha, at least 1 m³ in total) or at least 10 bird boxes per hectare of three different types (at least 10 in total).</p>	
0.8	<p>Three attributes present.</p>	<p>Forested gardens: three layers.</p>		<p>As condition class 1, but tree community is mostly of non-European origin.</p>
0.7				
0.6	<p>Two attributes present.</p> <p>Single invasive aliens plant species may be present.</p>		<p>Dead wood is either:</p> <p>a) large-diameter dead wood in marked quantities and two large-diameter dead wood structural attributes present,</p> <p>b) large-diameter dead wood to some extent (ca. 2–<5 m³/ha, at least 2 m³) and four large-diameter dead wood structural attributes present, or</p> <p>c) small-diameter dead wood in marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) and four dead wood structural attributes present.</p> <p>Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare of at least two different types (at least 5 boxes in total).</p>	<p>Most tree species are of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Tree community is either:</p> <p>a) even-aged, of a single species, and middle-aged but not old, or</p> <p>b) multispecied and comprises both young and middle-aged trees.</p>

0.5		Two layers.	As condition class 0.6, but no piles of rocks or other materials and no bird boxes.	
0.4	One attribute present. Several populations of invasive alien species may be present.		Large-diameter dead wood present to a degree, and large-diameter dead wood shows clear variation in one or minor variation in at least two structural attributes.	Tree community is mostly of Finnish or European origin. Tree community is either: a) even aged, of a single species, and middle-aged but not old, or b) young but multispecied.
0.3			Either: a) small quantities of or individual large-diameter dead wood objects, but dead wood shows clear variation in one or slight variation in at least two structural attributes; no piles of rocks or other materials or bird boxes, or b) small quantities of or individual large-diameter dead wood objects, dead wood does not exhibit variation in a single structural attribute, but site has marked piles of rocks or other materials or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare (at least 5 in total).	
0.2			Either: a) dead wood is scarce or only occurs as individual object, and dead wood does not exhibit variation in a single structural attribute, or b) No dead wood is present, but site has marked piles of rocks or other materials or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare (at least 5 in total).	
0.1		One layer.	No dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.	Tree community consists of even-aged young individuals of one non-European tree species.
0		Not a habitat type		

Picture 5. An allotment garden in Helsinki Central Park. Picture Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 6. An allotment garden with cottages. Picture Anna Pursiainen.

.Picture 7. An allotment garden in Järvenpää. Picture Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 8. Vallila Allotment Garden. Picture Anna Pursiainen.

Ground-contact yards

Description of habitat type

Ground-contact yards are the unconstructed and unpaved parts of residential, recreational, amenity, and work-place lots and city blocks. The yards are unpaved, i.e. are constructed directly on top of the ground. This habitat type does not include yards constructed on deck- or rooftops (see: Greenspace integrated into buildings and structures). Ground-contact yards include the yards of small residential buildings, apartment buildings, schools, and office buildings. The yards are usually private, managed by the property owners, and free access is not allowed.

Note that, especially in larger city blocks, the yard area, i.e. the unconstructed area, may be divided into several habitat types, such as parking lots (Street and square vegetation), courtyard decks (Greenspace integrated into buildings and structures), and ground-contact yards. The ground-contact yards of small residential buildings may, in principle, be demarcated as one habitat patch, but it may be practical to divide large block courtyards into several patches if the courtyard has several areas that differ in their ecological condition.

The amount and characteristics of ground-contact yard vegetation differ immensely based on yard maintenance, size, and age. The vegetation can be extensively managed, highly versatile and very diverse, and may include various planted, sown, and self-dispersed plants, shrubs, and trees. Useful plants can also be cultivated in small scale. Trees can be large in diameter and old, and yards can have abundant dead wood. On the other hand, yards can be intensively managed lawns and/or plantings and mostly paved, with very meagre vegetation. Ground-contact yards also exhibit unpredictability, as the yards and their vegetation can be altered greatly when ownership changes.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, a ground-contact yard has versatile and varied trees and vegetation. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. The site mostly has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plants and no invasive plant species. Plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants and trees are adapted to their living habitat and are viable. Canopy coverage ranges between 30% and 70%, and the site has microclimatically variable areas. The vegetation is clearly stratified into four layers. The trees are Finnish or European in species and origin, of multiple species, and of various ages. The site also has old trees. Dead wood is abundant, and it varies in terms of diameter, position, microclimate, species community, and especially decay stage. The trees have holes and/or cavities that create microhabitats. The site can also have piles of rocks or other materials, which offer shelter for animals. If the yard is treeless, it contains sun-loving plants and offers habitats for open habitat species. Site maintenance and management support the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

In the best scenario, these lush, multilayered, and diverse ground-contact yards support a diverse species composition. Flowering useful, ornamental, and other plants offer plentiful nutrition for pollinators. Abundant dead wood also supports pollinators in addition to a diverse wood-decay community. Rock walls and piles plus compost, leaf, and other heaps offer shelter and habitats for invertebrates. Dense, multilayered vegetation offers shelter and nesting sites for birds, mammals, and invertebrates. Old trees offer habitats for various epiphytic mosses and lichen, wood-decay and mycorrhiza fungi, and invertebrates. Many notable species typical in built environments live on the old and decaying hardwood trees.

Assessment tables for condition: Ground-contact yards

	Vegetation:	Forest structure	Canopy coverage	Vegetation stratification	Quantity and structural attributes of dead wood, and piles of rocks or other materials and bird boxes:
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) multispecied, 2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 4) sun-loving plants of barren environments 5) flowering is continuous from early to late summer 				<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) dead wood continuum 2) downed and standing dead wood 3) tree holes and cavities 4) variable microclimate of dead wood 5) dead wood comprises multiple species <p><i>Large-diameter dead wood: basal diameter ≥ 30 cm.</i></p> <p><i>Small-diameter dead wood: basal diameter 5–<30 cm.</i></p>
1	<p>At least four attributes present.</p> <p>No invasive alien plant species present.</p>	<p>Tree community is uneven-aged, and some trees are old according to species-specific standards.</p> <p>Tree community has multiple species.</p> <p>Most tree species are of Finnish or European origin.</p>	30–70%	Multilayered vegetation, four layers.	<p>Marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) of large-diameter dead wood and at least four structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, at least ca. 1 m³/ha of small-diameter dead wood.</p>
0.9					<p>Marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) of large-diameter dead wood and at three structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present.</p> <p>Additionally, at least ca. 1 m³/ha of small-diameter dead wood.</p> <p>Additionally, notable piles of rock or similar material (ca. 10 m³/ha, at least 1 m³ in total) or at least 10 bird boxes per hectare of three different types (at least 10 in total).</p>
0.8		As condition class 1, but tree community is mostly of non-European origin.		Three layers.	
0.7	Three attributes present.				
0.6	As condition class 0.7, but site has single invasive alien plant species.	<p>Tree community is mostly of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Tree community is either:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) even-aged, of a single species, and middle-aged but not old, or b) multispecied and comprises both young and middle-aged trees. 	>70%		<p>Dead wood is either:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) large-diameter dead wood in marked quantities and two large-diameter dead wood structural attributes present, b) large-diameter dead wood to some extent (ca. 2–<5 m³/ha, at least 2 m³) and four large-diameter dead wood structural attributes present, or c) small-diameter dead wood in marked quantities (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) and four dead wood structural attributes present. <p>Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials (ca. 5 m³/ha, at least 5 m³) or at least 5 bird boxes of at least two different types per hectare (at least 5 in total).</p>
0.5				Two layers.	As condition class 0.6, but no piles of rocks or other materials.
0.4	<p>Two attributes present.</p> <p>Several occurrences of invasive alien species may be present.</p>	<p>Tree community is mostly of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Tree community is either:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) even-aged, of a single species, and middle-aged but not old, or 	10– <30%		Large-diameter dead wood present to a degree, and large-diameter dead wood shows clear variation in one or minor variation in at least two structural attributes.

		b) multispecied and comprises both young and middle-aged trees.			
0.3					Either: a) small quantities of or individual large-diameter dead wood objects, but dead wood exhibits clear variation in one or slight variation in at least two structural attributes; no piles of rocks or other materials or bird boxes, or b) small quantities of or individual large-diameter dead wood objects, dead wood does not exhibit variation in a single structural attribute, but site has marked piles of rocks or other materials or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare (at least 5 in total).
0.2	One attribute present.				Either: a) dead wood is scarce or only occurs as individual objects, and dead wood does not exhibit variation in a single structural attribute, or b) no dead wood is present, but site has marked piles of rocks or other materials or at least 5 bird boxes per hectare (at least 5 in total).
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	No trees, or tree community is made up of young, even-aged individuals of a single tree species of non-European origin.	0%	One layer.	No dead wood, piles of rocks or other materials, or bird boxes present.
0		Not a habitat type			

Picture 9. Unpaved yard of a detached house. Picture. Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 10. Yard of a semidetached house in Helsinki. Picture. Anna Pursiainen

Picture 11. Unpaved courtyard of an apartment building. Picture Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 12. Fredrika Runeberg garden in Porvoo. Picture. Anna Pursiainen.

Shrub vegetation

Description of habitat type

Shrub vegetation is public or semi-public space that grows woody shrub vegetation reaching a maximum height of 5 metres that forks at the base, with a coverage of at least 30% of the surface area. The canopy coverage reaching above 5 metres is less than 10%. Dwarf shrubs are not considered shrubs in this categorization. Shrub vegetation also includes areas that currently do not fulfil the coverage criteria due to young age but will reach the criteria over time. Shrub vegetation can be so-called mass shrub plantings in green spaces. Shrub vegetation can also develop on spontaneously overgrowing ruderal sites or, for example, under powerlines. Shrub vegetation can often shift into forested parks as the trees grow (see Forested parks). This habitat type does not include berry plantings under active cultivation (see Gardens). This habitat type only includes shrubs that have developed in human-founded areas, and these should not be confused, for example, with shrub swamps that have developed naturally in flood-impacted areas or coastal *Juniperus communis* thickets.

Shrub vegetation changes with shrub coverage and soil. Vegetation in the herb and ground layers can be very meagre in shrub-covered areas, especially if the leaf matter and organic debris formed by the shrubs are not removed. In more open sites, the vegetation can include various herbaceous plants and/or mosses. Shrub vegetations are maintained by removing trees and/or shrubs.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, shrub vegetations have diverse and variable shrubs and vegetation. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. The site predominately has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plants and no invasive plant species. The plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants and trees are adapted to their living habitat and are viable. Canopy coverage ranges between 40% and 70%, and the site has microclimatically variable areas. The vegetation is clearly stratified into three layers. Dead wood from shrubs is allowed to accumulate on the site undisturbed, and various dead wood material is abundant. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity.

Shrub vegetation communities are not as biodiverse as the other forested habitat types in constructed environments. However, dense, versatile, and variable shrubs offer shelter and nesting sites for birds and other vertebrates. A dense shrub layer along with abundant leaf matter and dead wood matter accumulating on the ground offer habitats for diverse invertebrate assemblages. Shrub vegetation also supports unique dead wood communities specialized in shrub species.

Assessment tables for condition: Shrub vegetation

	Vegetation:	Shrub vegetation structure	Shrub vegetation coverage	Vegetation stratification	Dead wood
	<p>1) multispecied,</p> <p>2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species,</p> <p>3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants,</p> <p>4) flowering is continuous from early to late summer</p>				
1	Four attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	<p>Shrub vegetation is multispecied and uneven-aged, some shrubs are old according to species-specific standards.</p> <p>Shrub community is mostly of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Shrub vegetation is not intensively managed.</p>	40–70%	Multilayered vegetation, three layers.	<p>Abundant dead wood objects.</p> <p>Dead wood generation is natural, dead wood has not been cleared away.</p>
0.9					
0.8	Three attributes present.	<p>Shrub community is mostly of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Shrub vegetation is multispecied and uneven-aged, some shrubs are old according to species-specific standards.</p>			
0.7					
0.6	Two attributes present. Single invasive alien plant species may be present.	<p>Shrub community is mostly of Finnish or European origin.</p> <p>Shrub vegetation community is either:</p> <p>a) even-aged, single species, old according to species-specific standards, or</p> <p>b) multispecied and young</p>			
0.5			>70%	Two layers.	Dead wood is present, but it has been partially cleared away.
0.4	One attribute present. Several occurrences of invasive alien species may be present.				
0.3					
0.2					
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	Shrub vegetation consists of intensively managed, young, even-aged individuals of a single species of non-European origin.	30–40%	One layer.	No dead wood present.
0		Not a habitat type.			

Picture 13. A shrub as part of a pathway. Picture: Merete Kemppainen.

Picture 14. Flowering shrubs. Picture: Ella Lahtinen.

Picture 15: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 16. Common lilac. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Open parks

Description of habitat type

Open parks are open or sparsely wooded public or semi-public areas, where the canopy coverage of over 5-metre-tall trees is less than 10% (as opposed to forested parks; see Forested parks) and shrub vegetation coverage is less than 30% (as opposed to shrub vegetation land; see Shrub vegetation). The ground layer of this habitat type is unpaved, except for walking paths, contrary to squares (see Street and square vegetation). Open parks are typically used as green spaces for recreation, sports, and outing. This habitat type does not include open gardens cultivating useful plant (see Gardens).

The vegetation of open parks varies, especially according to maintenance and usage. Open parks can have extensive intensively managed lawns and grass fields but often also seasonal plantings of summer flowers, perennials, shrubs, and trees. Sites can also have extensively managed meadow-like or sun-loving vegetation.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, open parks have versatile and variable vegetation and habitats. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. Ideally, the vegetation of open parks is stratified, yet predominately the surface area is covered in open ground vegetation instead of shrubs. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plants and no invasive plant species. Plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants are adapted to their living habitat and are viable. The park terrain exhibits small-scale variation in topography and soil. The park gives mainly towards the south–southwest, offering warm and sun-drenched habitats. The site has large-diameter dead wood that varies in position and decay stage. The dead wood and living trees have holes and/or cavities that form microhabitats. The site also has piles of rocks or other materials, which offer shelter for animals. If the site has trees, they represent multiple species, are uneven-aged and old, and the site has hardwoods. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

In the best scenario, open parks offer habitat for the plant and insect communities of sun-drenched and other open habitats. Versatile flowering vegetation offers abundant nutrition for pollinators. Abundant dead wood also supports pollinators and a diverse wood-decay community of open habitats. Rock walls and piles offer shelter and habitat for animals and function as substrate for mosses, lichen, and rock plants. Old trees offer habitat for epiphytic mosses, lichen, wood-decay fungi, mycorrhiza fungi, and invertebrates. Especially old and decaying hardwood trees harbour many notable species of urban environments.

Assessment tables for condition: Open parks

	Vegetation:	Structural terrain attributes:	Quantity and structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials:	Tree community structure – only for forested sites
	1) multispecied, 2) stratification, 3) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 4) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 5) sun-loving species of barren environments, 6) flowering is continuous from early to late summer	1) landform variability, 2) soil variability, 3) warm microclimate (terrain orientation south–southwest)	1) dead wood continuum 2) downed and standing dead wood 3) tree holes and cavities <i>Large-diameter dead wood: basal diameter ≥ 30 cm.</i>	1) multiple tree species, 2) uneven-agedness of tree community, 3) old trees according to species-specific standards, 4) hardwood trees
1	At least four attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	Three structural attributes present.	Marked quantities (ca. 2 m ³ /ha, at least 2 m ³ in total) of large-diameter dead wood and two structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present. Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials.	Four structural attributes present.
0.9				
0.8				
0.7	Three attributes present.	Two attributes present.	Marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and two structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present. No piles of rocks or other materials.	Three structural attributes present.
0.6	As condition class 0.7, but site has single invasive alien plant species.			
0.5			Either: a) marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood, no structural attributes; no piles of rocks or other materials, or b) marked numbers of piles of rocks or other materials but no large-diameter dead wood.	
0.4	Two attributes present. Several occurrences of invasive alien species are possible.	One attribute present.		Two structural attributes present.
0.3				
0.2	One attribute present.			One attribute present.
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	No structural attributes present.	No large-diameter dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.	No structural attributes present.
0	Not a habitat type			

Picture 17. Picture: Anna Pursiainen

Picture 18. An open park in Tapiola. Picture: Anna Pursiainen

Picture 19. An open park in Tapiola. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 20. An open park in Tuusula. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Novel meadows

Description of habitat type

Novel meadows are public, semi-public, or private areas founded and maintained to recreate meadow and dry meadow habitats. The canopy coverage of over 5-metre-tall trees in novel meadows is 10% at most. The vegetation is partially or completely sown, or a designed meadow has been founded on top of a lawn through management practice changes. Novel meadows do not fulfil the foundation criteria of seminatural grasslands and grazed woodlands, i.e. they have not been under traditional non-eutrophication agricultural use, such as grazing and reaping, even though the same species can occur in both habitats. Of the RAMS categories (2020), high-value meadows, amenity meadows, and landscape meadows usually belong to this habitat type. A site where reaping or grazing has recently occurred and where the meadow species have not been sown is defined as a young seminatural grassland and grazed woodland, and its condition is assessed according to the ecological condition indicators (Jalkanen et al. 2026). Note that the "novel habitats" category used in traditional seminatural grassland and grazed woodland inventories (Kempainen 2017) can include novel meadows, road- and railside vegetation, parks, and other constructed environments described in this document.

The vegetation of novel meadows comprises species of seminatural grasslands and grazed woodlands, i.e. herbaceous melliferous plants and graminoids. The vegetation varies according to habitat and microclimate from sun-drenched to moist novel meadows. The vegetation can be partially naturally dispersed, but at least some of the meadow vegetation must originate from sowing. Novel meadows are maintained by reaping and less frequently by grazing. Reaping residues may be removed from the site.

The demarcation between novel meadows and other constructed habitats can be flexible, as, for example, the aim may be to increase and maintain meadow vegetation in ground-contact yards and forested and open parks. A site is defined as a designed meadow if it is created with the intent of founding a designed meadow by sowing or by rewilding lawns, if the site resembles a meadow, dry meadow, or other seminatural grassland or grazed woodland in terms of its species community, if site maintenance clearly aims to found and uphold a meadow or dry meadow, and if the site is of a size that is sensible to demark as its own site (normative site size is ca. 0.1 ha.) However, meadow-like or dry meadow-like road- and railside vegetation is not classified as novel meadows (see Road- and railside vegetation) unless they have been specifically established as novel meadows, which is also accounted for in their maintenance. Meadows established on decks and green roofs are always considered to be vegetation integrated into buildings and structures (see Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures).

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, the vegetation of novel meadows resembles that of seminatural grasslands and grazed woodlands and offers habitats for species dependent on such environments. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plants, notable species of seminatural grasslands and grazed woodlands, and no invasive plants. Plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and may produce winter forage for other animals. The soil, moisture, terrain, and other conditions enable the development and upholding of a representative community of seminatural grassland and grazed woodland species. The site can also have individual old trees. The site can have large-diameter dead wood that varies in position and decay stage. The dead and living trees have holes and/or cavities that form microhabitats. The site can also have piles of rocks or other materials, which offer shelter for animals. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values. Moisture conditions are stable, especially in moist novel meadows, ensuring that moist meadow species can become established.

In the best scenario, a novel meadow can strongly resemble a sun-drenched habitat, such as rocky dry meadows or esker meadows, grazing meadows or wooded pastures formed through long-term grazing, or moist meadows, such as shore meadows or mesic meadows, if the maintenance and environmental factors of the designed meadow so allow. The seeds of nearby meadow vegetation populations can be used to establish novel meadows, thereby supporting genetic diversity. The plant and animal communities of the most representative novel meadows cannot be separated from the communities of seminatural grasslands and grazed woodlands, and novel meadows can function as habitats for demanding and/or threatened sun-loving, dry meadow, and meadow species.

Assessment tables for condition: Dry novel meadows

	Vegetation and other notable communities:	Structural attributes of dry novel meadows:
	<p>1) multispecied,</p> <p>2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species,</p> <p>3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants,</p> <p>4) flowering is continuous from early to late summer</p> <p>5) especially notable community (especially notable meadow plant species, listed in Kemppainen 2017, or other notable site for threatened seminatural grassland and grazed woodland species).</p>	<p>1) sandy soil,</p> <p>2) sun-drenched conditions,</p> <p>3) landform variability,</p> <p>4) patchy bare ground,</p> <p>5) large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials</p> <p>6) single old tree individuals</p>
1	<p>Four attributes present, and additionally site is important for especially notable species.</p> <p>No invasive alien plant species present.</p>	<p>The following structural attributes are fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land.</p> <p>Additionally, either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials, or single old tree individuals.</p>
0.9	<p>Four other attributes present, but site is not important for especially notable species.</p> <p>No invasive alien plant species present.</p>	
0.8		<p>The following structural attributes are fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land.</p>
0.7		
0.6	<p>Three attributes present.</p> <p>Single invasive aliens plant species may be present.</p>	<p>Three of the following structural attributes are fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land.</p> <p>Additionally, either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials, or single old tree individuals.</p>
0.5		<p>Three of the following structural attributes are fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land.</p>
0.4	<p>Two attributes present.</p> <p>Several populations of invasive alien species may be present.</p>	<p>Either:</p> <p>a) two of the following structural attributes are fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land, or</p> <p>b) one of the following structural attributes is fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land and, additionally, either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials or single old tree individuals.</p>
0.3		<p>One of the following structural attributes is fulfilled: sandy soil, sun-drenched conditions, landform variability, and patchy bare land</p>
0.2	<p>One attribute present.</p>	<p>Either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials or single old tree individuals.</p>
0.1	<p>No attributes present.</p> <p>Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.</p>	<p>No structural attributes present.</p>
0	<p>Not a habitat type</p>	

Assessment tables for condition: Mesic and moist novel meadows

	Vegetation and other notable communities:	Structural attributes of mesic novel meadows:
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) multispecied, 2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 4) flowering is continuous from early to late summer, 5) especially notable community (notable meadow plant species, listed in Kemppainen 2017, or otherwise notable site for threatened seminatural grassland and grazed woodland species). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) landform variability, 2) patchy bare ground, 3) large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials 4) single old tree individuals
1	Four attributes present, and additionally site is important for especially notable species. No invasive alien plant species present.	Landform variability and patch bare ground are fulfilled. Additionally, either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials, or single old tree individuals.
0.9	Four other attributes present, but site is not important for especially notable species. No invasive alien plant species present.	
0.8		Landform variability and patch bare ground are fulfilled.
0.7		
0.6	Three attributes present. Single invasive aliens plant species may be present.	Either the criterion for landform variability or patchy bare ground is fulfilled. Additionally, either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials, or single old tree individuals.
0.5		Either landform variability or patch bare ground is fulfilled.
0.4	Two attributes present. Several populations of invasive alien species may be present.	
0.3		Marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials, and single old tree individuals.
0.2		Either marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials or single old tree individuals.
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	No structural attributes present.
0	Not a habitat type	

Picture 21. A transferred designedl meadow in Tampere. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Picture 22. A designed meadow in Viikki, Helsinki. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Picture 23. A designed meadow in a residential neighbourhood. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Picture 24. A sun-drenched urban meadow in Tampere. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Ruderal areas

Description of habitat type

Ruderal areas are idle land that has experienced considerable soil alteration through human action. Ruderal areas develop on land that has experienced soil tillage or piling, where relatively little time has passed since the modifying activities. Ruderal areas are naturally open space, and they usually develop on their own as a secondary result of human activity. Examples of typical areas where ruderal lands form are the outskirts of storage fields and industrial areas, snow drop zones, abandoned construction sites or gravel pits, piling areas, and artificial hills. Ruderal areas can also be established on bare, vegetation-free land. However, ruderal areas do not include piling and excavation sites in active use, where vegetation cannot establish due to human activity (see Habitats created through industrial processes).

As succession progresses, unmanaged and undisturbed ruderal land can develop into shrub vegetation (see Shrub vegetation; shrub coverage $\geq 30\%$) or forested parks (see Forested parks; canopy coverage $\geq 10\%$).

Ruderal vegetation can be very diverse and varied. The vegetation often comprises both dispersing pioneer species and germinated plants originating from a seed bank in the soil brought onto the site. Ruderal plant communities are therefore often a mixture of wild species and garden plants. Ruderal sites may exhibit very small-scale variation in the topsoil, thereby creating versatile growing conditions. Sometimes small wetlands can develop on ruderal sites, for example in clay recesses.

Ruderal land does not usually belong under maintenance practices but can occasionally be maintained by reaping and removing shrubs and tree saplings (compare with open parks and novel meadows, which are regularly managed by reaping). Ruderal areas are also upheld when the soil is tilled or new earth material is transported onto the site.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, a ruderal site has versatile and varied vegetation and habitats. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. The site has wild and non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plant species, and no invasive alien plants. The plants produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants are adapted to their environment and are viable. The terrain exhibits small-scale topographical and soil variation. Ruderal sites are predominantly open and sun-drenched, but some shrubs also occur. The soil comprises various uncontaminated earth materials with small-scale variation. Any possible maintenance and management measures uphold the preservation and development of the site's biodiversity values.

In the best scenario, ruderal sites are very diverse and unique habitats in terms of species. The vegetation can be highly diverse and contain plants from different habitats due to versatile seed banks. Small-scale variations in soil and vegetation succession add to the versatility and biodiversity of ruderal sites. Invertebrate communities are also highly diverse. The winter-persistent seed heads of large ruderal areas are a notable winter food source for passerine birds.

Assessment tables for condition: Ruderal areas

	Vegetation:	Structural attributes:	Soil contamination and level of littering
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) multispecied, 2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 4) sun-loving species of barren habitats, 5) flowering is continuous from early to late summer 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) openness (canopy coverage <10%) 2) both sparse shrubs and bare ground, 3) landform variation, 4) soil variation 	
1	At least four attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	At least four attributes present.	Topsoil is uncontaminated throughout, and site does not exhibit littering at levels detrimental to ruderal vegetation.
0.9			
0.8	Three attributes present.		
0.7		Three structural attributes present.	
0.6	Two attributes present. Single invasive aliens plant species may be present.		
0.5		Two structural attributes present.	Contaminated topsoil has been remediated or share of contaminated soil is very small. Site may exhibit littering that is somewhat detrimental to the formation of representative ruderal vegetation.
0.4	One attribute present. Several occurrences of invasive alien species may be present.		
0.3		One structural attribute present.	
0.2			
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	No structural attributes present.	Topsoil is visibly contaminated and/or site is so littered that it prevents the formation of representative ruderal vegetation.
0		Not an habitat type	

Picture 25. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 26. A flowering ruderal site. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Picture 27. A ruderal site in Leppävaara, Espoo. Picture: Merete Kemppainen.

Picture 28. Picture: Johanna Huttunen.

Fields

Description of habitat type

Field is a general term for cultivation areas under agricultural use that are actively modified and upheld according to crop rotation cycles. In addition to cultivated fields, this habitat type also includes pastures, fallow land, and food plots. Especially in urban areas, fields can be kept to uphold scenic and cultural-historical values. Fields classified as scenic fields according to the RAMS classification belong to this habitat type. Fallow and scenic fields and field pastures are differentiated from seminatural grasslands, grazed woodlands, and novel meadows because areas belonging to the field habitat type have previously been cultivated as fields and are under crop rotation or can still be used for active cultivation. Fields do not include vegetable gardens or other small-scale cultivation areas for useful plants or shrubs or orchards reserved for growing berries or fruit (see Gardens).

A practical habitat unit for assessing the ecological condition of fields can be very large, at least one field parcel in size.

Field ditches and other ditches are classified under artificial wetlands (see Artificial wetlands). However, usually there is no need to separately demarcate these small channels; rather, they can be included in the field parcel. In this case, the biodiversity of the field area is increased by the potential wetland vegetation. However, small wetland channels or depressions that are in particularly good condition and that clearly stand out from the rest of the habitat or that are otherwise notable should be demarcated as their own sites.

Description of ideal ecological condition

Field utilization is inevitably a balance between cultivation needs and biodiversity along with other needs and viewpoints. From an ecological viewpoint, a long-term fallow field or food plot represents an ideal field type. In an ideal situation, an active field is cultivated using natural methods, the cultivation considers biodiversity factors, and fertilization is based on crop rotation or on the grazing of other animals than dairy cattle. At least three perennial plants are cultivated on the field. The field is topographically varied and includes sandy soil. The field or its margins has open ditches and seasonal wetland depressions, individual trees and/or woodland patches, and piles of rocks or other materials. Cultivation methods support natural biodiversity, for example by delaying the cultivation of spring-moist areas. If the site is under grazing, the area has vegetation coverage throughout (no overgrazing).

In the best scenario, fields support a multitude of plant, bird, and invertebrate communities and soil biota of seminatural grasslands and grazed woodlands. Fields cultivating insect-pollinated plants, fallow fields, and pastures support considerable levels of pollinating invertebrates in addition to birds that consume these invertebrates, and considerable levels of other animals. At its best, the soil biota of fields is diverse and viable.

Assessment tables for condition: Fields

	Multiple species of cultivated/planted vegetation	Structural attributes: 1) sandy or silty soil, 2) open ditches, 3) woodland patches, 4) seasonal moisture, 5) single trees, 6) hilly terrain	Natural cultivation and fertilization	Quantity and structural attributes of dead wood and piles of rocks or similar materials: 1) dead wood continuum 2) downed and standing dead wood 3) tree holes and cavities <i>Large-diameter dead wood: basal diameter ≥ 30 cm.</i>
1	Diverse, multispecied, perennial vegetation. No invasive alien species.	At least five structural attributes present.	Natural cultivation (organic field).	Marked quantities (ca. 2 m ³ /ha, at least 2 m ³) of large-diameter dead wood and two structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present. Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials.
0.9				
0.8		Four structural attributes present.		
0.7	Multispecied scenic field.			Marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and two structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present. No piles of rocks or other materials.
0.6	As condition class 0.7, but site has individual invasive alien plant species.	Three structural attributes present.		
0.5			Either: a) will be placed under organic cultivation, b) is under permanent grazing without supplemental fertilization; however, not a pasture for dairy cattle.	Either: a) marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood, no structural attributes; no piles of rocks or other materials, or b) marked numbers of piles of rocks or other materials but no large-diameter dead wood.
0.4	Insect-pollinated plants cultivated in monocultures. Several occurrences of invasive alien species can be present.	Two attributes present.		
0.3				
0.2		One attribute present.		
0,1	Wind-pollinated plants cultivated in monocultures. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	No structural attributes present.	No natural cultivation.	No large-diameter dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.
0	Not a habitat type			

Picture 29. A field in Liesjärvi. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 30. A field in Malmi, Helsinki. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 31. Berry pickers on a strawberry field in Tuusula. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 32. A field in Hyvinkää. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Road- and railside vegetation

Description of habitat

This habitat type includes the vegetation in the immediate surroundings along major traffic routes, i.e. highways, trunk routes, and other large roads and rail lines. The habitat type includes various road shoulders, ramps, embankments, and vegetated noise barriers. The areas in-between interchanges as well as railway yards also belong to this habitat type. The buffer zones of traffic routes are not automatically included, as they usually belong to some other habitat type such as forests or forested parks.

This habitat type is bound to large traffic routes, which determine the habitat's characteristic microclimatic and management conditions. The width of roadside verges can vary greatly. Embankment bridges or noise barriers can be tens of metres in width. On the other hand, the roadside verges along smaller routes or the areas bordering forested buffer zones can be narrow.

Assessing the ecological condition of roadside verges is based on sections with uniform characteristics. The roadside verge under assessment should therefore be divided into uniform sections based on vegetation, soil, microclimate, and other relevant factors, and the ecological condition of these sections must be evaluated separately.

Major traffic routes often have various roadside stormwater channels and ditches, which are classified as artificial wetlands (see Artificial wetlands). However, it is usually not necessary to separately demarcate these small channels; rather, they can be included in the roadside verge sites. In this case, any possible wetland vegetation increases the diversity of the road- and railside vegetation. However, small wetland channels or depressions that are in particularly good condition and that clearly stand out from the rest of the habitat or that are otherwise notable should be demarcated as their own sites even if they are part of a roadside verge.

The vegetation varies from lawns and planted shrub vegetation to naturally spreading meadow-like and sun-loving vegetation and forested spaces and shrub vegetation. The top earth materials of this habitat type can vary from crushed stone to recycled materials, such as crushed concrete, or natural topsoils such as sand or moraine soil and clay. Noise barrier construction, in particular, often utilizes various crushed materials and landfill, which impacts the area's vegetation.

Traffic route maintenance, such as salting in winter, impacts the vegetation along roadside verges. The vegetation is actively maintained to ensure traffic safety. Road- and railside vegetation is mowed regularly, and all saplings are crushed. The inner spaces of intersections and junctions are also maintained actively, although their maintenance is more infrequent than that alongside traffic routes.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, roadside verges are open environments that offer habitat to sun-loving plant species and other species. The site does not have tree or shrub overgrowth. The vegetation is diverse, with small-scale and mosaic variation. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plant species and no harmful invasive plants. Plants produce nutrition to pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The site has large-diameter dead wood that varies in position and decay stage. The dead wood and living trees have holes and/or cavities that form microhabitats. The site also has piles of rocks or other materials, which offer shelter for animals. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

In the best scenario, if a site's management and environmental factors (especially the top earth layer) allow, roadside verges offer notable support to the plant and insect communities of sun-drenched areas and dry semi-natural grasslands and grazed woodlands, such as dry meadows. Roadside verges, especially railway yards, have abundant non-invasive synanthropic and adventive species, along with their companion insect species, which enrich Finnish plant communities.

Assessment tables for condition: Road- and railside vegetation

	Vegetation: 1) multispecied, 2) sun-loving species of barren habitats, 3) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 4) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 5) flowering is continuous from early to late summer	Overgrowth	Quantity and structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials: 4) dead wood continuum 5) downed and standing dead wood 6) tree holes and cavities <i>Large-diameter dead wood: basal diameter ≥ 30 cm.</i>
1	At least four attributes present. No invasive alien species.	No overgrowth.	Marked quantities (ca. 2 m ³ /ha, at least 2 m ³ in total) of large-diameter dead wood and two structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present. Additionally, notable piles of rocks or other materials.
0.9			
0.8			
0.7	Three attributes present.	Intermittent overgrowth.	Marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood and two structural attributes of large-diameter dead wood present. No piles of rocks or other materials.
0.6	As condition class 0.7, but area has occurrences of invasive alien plants.		
0.5			Either: a) marked quantities of large-diameter dead wood, no structural attributes; no piles of rocks or other materials, or b) marked numbers of piles of rocks or other materials but no large-diameter dead wood.
0.4	Two attributes present. Several occurrences of invasive alien species are possible.		
0.3		Pronounced overgrowth.	
0.2	One attribute.		
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	Fully overgrown.	No large-diameter dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.
0		Not a habitat type	

Picture 33. Road- and railside vegetation in Espoo. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 34. Flowering vegetation along a ring road. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Vegetation of streets and squares

Description of habitat

This habitat type includes the vegetation growing in the unpaved spaces along streets and in squares, parking lots, and similar areas. The habitat type does not include the roadside verges of major traffic routes (see Road- and railside vegetation). The habitat type also does not include potted plantings in streets or squares or other transportable non-ground-bearing structures (see Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures).

The growing conditions on streets, squares, and parking lots are often challenging due to road salt, sun-drenched conditions, and limited growing space. The vegetation has been planted or sown and may include individual trees, various green verges along streets and parking lots, or the green tracks of tram routes. The vegetation varies from lawns to weeds and meadow-like spaces and from mass-planted shrubs to dynamic multispecies shrub and perennial plantings. Street spaces, squares, parking lots, and other spaces included in this habitat type mostly comprise paved space. Sometimes the only vegetation is trees, and the ground surface is otherwise paved.

The vegetated zones of street areas can comprise various planting strips and spaces. Often it is not feasible to separately demarcate such very small green strips as their own sites. Rather, street areas are divided into uniform sections according to structure and condition. All the vegetated zones within a section are defined as one plot. Accordingly, squares, parking lots etc. are defined as individual sites, whose vegetated zones are considered sub-plots. In this manner, the condition classes for a street section or a square plot are defined as an entity for the entire site. The surface area of street sections, squares, and other demarcated sites is calculated solely based on their vegetated area. With intersecting streets, care should be taken to calculate the vegetation in the crossing only once.

Trees can be planted on streets and squares despite the area otherwise being completely paved. This creates challenges for calculating habitat hectares. In this case, the ecological condition indicators can exceptionally be assessed into condition class 0, except for canopy coverage and forest structure, because the ground layer has no surface suitable for nature. The canopy coverage indicator is assessed for the entire street section, square etc. The forest structure indicator is assessed normally according to tree attributes. In this case, the green space surface area for the site (i.e. the area based on which habitat hectares are calculated) is determined according to the number of tree individuals. One tree roughly corresponds to 1 m² of green-covered ground, i.e. 0.0001 ha.

Habitat hectares are calculated using the formula:

$(\text{condition class for canopy coverage} + \text{condition class for forest structure})/5 \times [\text{number of all indicators}] \times \text{number of trees} + 0.0001$.

For example, assume two equal-length street sections. The total canopy coverage of both streets is 60%, which corresponds to condition class 0.8 for the canopy coverage indicator. Both streets have a row of maples. The trees are 15 cm in diameter, which corresponds to condition class 0.5 for the forest structure indicator. Both streets have 50 trees.

On the first street, the maples have been planted along a green strip on the street side. The surface area of the green strip is 100 m², i.e. 0.01 ha. The green strip comprises intensively managed lawn, so the condition classes for its vegetation, vegetation stratification, and dead wood and rock pile indicators are each assessed to be 0.1.

In this case, the habitat hectares for the first street are:

$(0.8 [\text{canopy coverage}] + 0.5 [\text{tree community}] + 0.1 [\text{vegetation}] + 0.1 [\text{vegetation stratification}] + 0.1 [\text{dead wood}])/5 \times 0.01 [\text{green space surface area}] = 0.0116 \text{ habitat hectares}$.

Except for the trees, the second street is completely paved.

In this case, the habitat hectares for the first street are:

$(0.8 [\text{canopy coverage}] + 0.5 [\text{tree community}] + 0 [\text{vegetation}] + 0 [\text{vegetation stratification}] + 0 [\text{dead wood}])/5 \times 50 [\text{number of trees}] \times 0.0001 [\text{green space surface area per tree}] = 0.0013 \text{ habitat hectares}$.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, the vegetation of streets, squares, and parking lots is versatile and varying. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plant species and no invasive plant species. Plants produce nutrition for pollinators and other animals. The vegetation is clearly stratified into four layers. The site has piles of rocks and dead wood that function as microhabitats. If the street or square has trees, canopy coverage is high. The tree community is diverse, including native Finnish or European tree species, trees with diameters over 20 cm, and trees that are insect pollinated or produce berries and/or fruit. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

The vegetation of streets and squares offers only slight support to biodiversity when compared with the other habitat types of built environments. The species communities of street areas and squares are typically generalists with high dispersal capability. However, melliferous plants or plants offering other types of nutrition in street areas offer extra nutrition to animals, substrate for various epiphytic mosses and lichen, and shelter for various invertebrates. Therefore, the vegetation of streets and squares supplements the environments and nutrition offered by other green spaces but does not replace them.

Assessment tables for condition: Vegetation of streets and squares

	Vegetation: 1) multispecied, 2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 4) sun-loving species of barren habitats	Vegetation stratification	Dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials	Forest structure – only for forested sites: 1) tree width, 2) multispecied, 3) community mostly of European origin	Canopy coverage of street area or square – only for forested sites
1	At least three attributes present. No invasive alien species.	Multilayered vegetation, at least three layers.	Both dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials.	Notable share of tree community is of Finnish or European origin. Tree community has multiple species. Trees are over 20 cm in diameter or, for naturally narrow-trunked tree species, trees are thickish.	>70%
0.9					
0.8					30–70%
0.7	Two attributes present.			Notable share of tree community is of Finnish or European origin. Tree community is either of a single species and over 20 cm in diameter or is multispecied and under 20 cm in diameter (with naturally narrow-trunked tree species, trees are thickish according to species-specific standards).	
0.6	As condition class 0.7, but site has individual invasive alien plants.				
0.5	One attribute.	Two layers.	Dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.	Notable share of tree community is of Finnish or European origin. Tree community has multiple species. Tree community is either of a single species and over 15 cm in diameter or multispecied and under 15 cm in diameter (naturally narrow-trunked tree species are not thickish according to species-specific standards).	10–<30%
0.4	A condition class 0.5., but site has several occurrences of invasive alien plants.				
0.3					
0.2					
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	One layer.	No dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.	Tree community comprises individuals of one non-European species that are under 10 cm in diameter (naturally narrow-trunked species are narrow according to species-specific standards).	1–<10%
0	Not a habitat type				

Picture 35. Street vegetation at Konepaja, Helsinki. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 36. Street vegetation along a tram route in Helsinki. Picture: Olivia Mahlio.

Picture 37. Street vegetation along Hermannin rantatie in Helsinki. Kuva Olivia Mahlio.

Picture 38. Flowering street trees in Lauttasaari, Helsinki. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures

Description of habitat

This habitat type includes vegetation on building roofs and walls, such as decked courtyards, green roofs and walls, and various structures with integrated vegetation, such as transportable green walls and potted plantings. The growing medium for the vegetation has been transported onto the site and is not connected to the soil. The habitat type also includes (brick) walls that grow vascular plants, mosses, and/or lichen, even in cases where the vegetation has self-dispersed onto the surface. This habitat type also includes walls used to grow climbing plants planted in the ground. In the case of walls etc., the surface area of the site is calculated according to the vertical surface area of the structure.

Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures varies according to the growing medium and management. The vegetation is commonly at least partially planted or sown but can also have self-dispersed. The vegetation can comprise very low-lying stonecrop or moss roofs or it can contain lawns, meadow-like spaces, and various plantings and/or weeds. The vegetation of thicker growing media, such as in decked courtyards, can be lush, multilayered, and be comprised of shrubs and small trees. Many potted plantings contain seasonal plants that can be switched several times a year. The vegetation integrated into buildings and structures is commonly temporary and requires renewal once the service life of the building or structure comes to an end.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, the vegetation integrated into buildings and structures is versatile and varying. The growing medium is deep enough for lush and multilayered vegetation and small trees. The site has wild and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte plant species and no invasive alien plants. The plants and trees produce nutrition for pollinators throughout the summer and winter forage for other animals. The plants and trees are adapted to their living habitat and are viable. The vegetation is clearly stratified into at least three layers. The site has piles of rocks and dead wood that function as microhabitats. Site maintenance and management uphold the preservation and development of biodiversity values.

Even in the best scenario, the vegetation integrated into buildings and structures offers only fairly versatile support to regular species communities. However, the layered vegetation, dead wood, piles of rocks, and plants and trees offering nectar or other nutrition offer additional nutrition and shelter for animals. For example, gulls and oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus*) can nest on roofs in coastal cities. In the best scenario, sun-drenched green roofs support sun-loving plant and insect communities. The vegetation integrated into buildings and structures can therefore supplement the environments and nutrition offered by other green spaces despite not replacing them. The temporary nature of the vegetation structures integrated into buildings and structures decreases their potential support to biodiversity.

Assessment tables for condition: Vegetation integrated into buildings and structures

	Vegetation:	Vegetation stratification	Dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials
	1) multispecied, 2) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 3) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 4) sun-loving species of barren habitats 5) flowering is continuous from early to late summer		
1	Four attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	Multilayered vegetation, at least three layers.	Both dead wood and piles of rocks or other materials.
0.9			
0.8	Three attributes present.		
0.7			
0.6	Two attributes present. Single invasive alien plant species may be present.		
0.5		Two layers.	Dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.
0.4	One attribute present. Several populations of invasive alien species may be present.		
0.3			
0.2			
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	One layer.	No dead wood or piles of rocks or other materials.
0	Not a habitat type.		

Picture 39. Cultivation boxes. Picture: Antti Hannula.

Picture 40. Näsi park bridge in Tampere. Picture: Ella Lahtinen.

Picture 41. Integrated vegetation in Urheilupuisto, Espoo. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 42. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Habitats created through industrial processes

Description of habitat type

This habitat type includes various areas for earthworks, aggregate extraction, piling and storage, mines, quarries etc. that are in active industrial use. Due to their active use, the sites are not stable, and the aggregates can shift at any time. Therefore, the vegetation of these areas is unestablished and may consist of rapidly spreading pioneer plants or be completely missing. This habitat type does not include landscaped areas once under industrial use because some other habitat type, such as a designed meadow (see Novel meadows) or a forest, is founded on the site during the landscaping. Industrial areas, business logistics areas etc., whose industrial use does not directly uphold environmental conditions, are also not included in this habitat type. Rock face excavations are assessed using the criteria in the Red Book of habitat types regarding rock face habitats (Jalkanen et al. 2026). Scrap and waste management areas are also not included in the habitat type.

Once industrial use has ended, these areas can quickly transform into other habitat types, especially into ruderal sites (see Ruderal sites) or wetlands (see Artificial wetlands). Ruderal sites often form on the fringes of environments under industrial use if soil is present. With consideration, such subplots can be included into the green space sites formed by industrial processes, especially if the ruderal patches are characteristically temporary and will be taken into industrial use at a future date.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, habitats created through industrial processes offer habitats to plants and animals despite the industrial activity. The earth is mainly gravel, sand, or calcareous materials. Industrial use is not continuous but rather often pauses overnight or during the nesting periods of animals, and the activity also does not target the entire area at once. Despite the industrial use, some naturally occurring vegetation that includes plants in sun-drenched habitats occurs on the site. The site does not have invasive plant species.

The habitat type has limited capacity to support biodiversity, as the industrial use prevents the vegetation and other species communities from establishing on the site. However, areas under industrial use can offer nesting sites to the fauna of open areas if the industrial use is not excessively intensive during the nesting period. Such species include birds nesting on sand bluffs, open land, and rocky ground, such as bank swallows (*Riparia riparia*), wheatears (*Oenanthe oenanthe*), white wagtails (*Motacilla alba*), or little ringed plovers (*Charadrius dubius*), or insects living in open areas such as *Cardiophorus asellus*, *Sphingonotus caeruleus*, *Caryocolum fischerella*, and *Coleophora filaginella*. Sites that handle calcareous landmasses or materials can offer habitats to calciphilous plants.

Assessment tables for condition: Habitats created through industrial processes

	Vegetation: 1) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 2) melliferous plants and/or forage plants, 3) sun-loving species of barren habitats	Soil material quality	Prevalence of disturbances	Nesting and living sites
1	Three attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	Gravel, sand, or calcareous soil material.	Periodical disturbances (e.g. not around the clock or on every day of the week). Site also has subareas experiencing less disturbances/use.	Site offers breeding area for species of open spaces, sandy areas, or scree. Industrial use of site enables nesting of species.
0.9				
0.8				
0.7	Two attributes present.			
0.6	As condition class 0.7, but area has occurrences of invasive aliens plants.			
0.5	One attribute present.	Some other stone aggregate, soil material, or crushed aggregate than in condition classes 1 and 0.1.		
0.4	As condition class 0.5, but site has several occurrences of invasive alien plants.			
0.3				
0.2				
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	Clay, ash, or slag.	Disturbances are round-the-clock and continuous.	Site does not offer a breeding area for species of open spaces, sandy areas, scree etc.
0		Not an habitat type		

Picture 43. Picture: Johanna Huttunen.

Picture 44. Picture: Johanna Huttunen

Picture 45. Picture: Riku Lumiaro.

Artificial wetlands

Description of habitat

This habitat type includes areas permanently or seasonally covered by water that have wetland vegetation and that have been constructed by humans or that have formed due to human activity. The habitat type also includes the immediate shoreline surrounding a wetland. This habitat type is quite broad. The habitat type includes wetlands constructed to naturally delay and filter stormwater as well as depressions and ponds. It also includes artificial seasonal channels, such as stormwater channels and field ditches. Wetlands formed through human activity include repeatedly flooding and alluvial wetlands unintentionally formed during roadway construction or other construction and peat production areas that have been restored into wetlands or have formed into wetlands on their own. A wetland complex can include seasonal wetlands, small ponds and bog pools, and channels leading water in or out of the wetland. If ecologically justified, small islets permanently above the waterline or wider shore areas can also be included into wetland complexes.

Small stormwater channels or ditches are often permanently incorporated into constructed areas. For example, roadsides along traffic routes commonly have stormwater depressions and ditches, fields in ideal condition have frequent field ditches, and parks and yards can have small wetland features. These small wetland channels or depressions usually do not need to be demarcated separately but can rather be included in the habitat types of constructed environments (e.g. road- and railside vegetation, fields, yards). However, small wetland channels or depressions that are in particularly good ecological condition and that clearly stand out from the rest of the habitat or that are otherwise notable should be demarcated as their own sites even if they are part of another habitat type. Broad wetland areas should also be demarcated separately.

Artificial wetlands do not include water basins, whose hydrology is actively regulated (see Artificial water basins). Human-constructed or -founded water basins that are analogous to natural ponds in terms of size, depth, and hydrology are defined as artificial ponds, whose condition is assessed using the criteria for natural ponds (Jalkanen et al. 2026). Constantly moist or usually non-seasonal artificial running water channels are defined as human-founded running water, whose condition is assessed using the criteria of natural running waters (Jalkanen et al. 2026).

The vegetation of artificial wetlands can consist of shore, water, peatland, and/or alluvial vegetation. The sites can also have trees and shrubs. The vegetation can be planted, sown, or naturally dispersed.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, artificial wetlands offer versatile habitats for aquatic and shore species. Wetland vegetation is versatile and varying and comprises both aquatic and shore vegetation. Melliferous plants also occur. The site does not have invasive alien plants. The wetland has water year-round, and water quality is not poor due to watershed status. The bottom and shore profile of the wetland exhibit small-scale variation. The shore zone and adjacent habitat create a sheltered microclimate for the wetland and function as a habitat.

In the best scenario, artificial wetlands offer habitat to diverse aquatic and shore communities. Water basins offer habitats to a multitude of aquatic invertebrates and a breeding site for aquatic egg layers. The vegetation and fauna of the shore zone are also diverse. Wide wetland areas offer nesting sites to aquatic and shore birds and mammals. Wetlands in an ideal condition are notable habitats for amphibians.

Assessment tables for condition: Artificial wetlands

	Vegetation: 1) multispecied, 2) versatility (includes shore plants, helophytes, floating-leaved plants, submerged plants), 3) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 4) melliferous plants	Bottom structure	Water permanence	Watershed	Condition of adjacent zone <i>Adjacent zone: area that has a direct influence on the site</i>
1	Four attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	Wetland bottom and shore profile are varying and versatile. Wetland does not have apparent filter fabrics, pool plastics, or similar materials.	Site has water year-round.	Loading from watershed is not marked, and site has abundant permeable surface and vegetation.	Shore zone and adjacent zone have abundant tall trees and/or other sheltering vegetation, and share of permeable surface is large.
0.9					
0.8	Three attributes present.				
0.7					
0.6	Two attributes present. Single invasive aliens plant species may be present.	Either the bottom or the shore profile varies to a degree and the wetland does not appear to have filter fabric or similar, or the bottom and the shore profile varies like in condition class 1 but the wetland has a filter fabric or similar.			
0.5			Site is dry occasionally, for example a few weeks during dry summers.		Shore zone and adjacent zone have at least some tall or short sheltering vegetation and a partially permeable surface.
0.4	One attribute present. Several occurrences of invasive alien species may be present.				
0.3					
0.2					
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	The bottom and shore profiles are very uniform and do not vary at all. Filter fabric or similar may be present.	Site has water only intermittently, for example after heavy rains or flooding.	Watershed has very strong sources of loading, such as heavy industry, mining activities, or very heavily trafficked roads, little permeable surface, and/or site is located on contaminated soil.	Shore zone and zone habitat is completely devoid of vegetation and share of permeable surface is small.
0		Not a habitat type			

Picture 46. Stormwater wetland, Vauhantie, Helsinki. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 47. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 48. Wetland in Kerava. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 49. Wetland in Kotka. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Artificial shores

Description of habitat type

This habitat type includes artificial shores founded on the landfills of water systems. The habitat type only includes shore areas that are located on new shoreline constructed completely by humans. The habitat type should therefore be differentiated from modified natural shores, which are assessed using the criteria of natural shores (Jalkanen et al. 2026). Note that shore habitat types with degraded ecological condition can be very strongly modified (e.g. embankments). In practice, the decisive factor distinguishing between natural shores and artificial shores is solely whether the shore is located on extensive landfill or not. Landfill origin information may be a prerequisite, or this information can be ascertained, for example, from old aerial photographs. This habitat type does not include completely paved or unvegetated sites such as concrete or brick seawalls.

Artificial shores include the ecotone between land and water (the littoral zone), as do natural shore habitats. Artificial shores vary in both their above- and underwater elements, from highly constructed and uniform embankment, gravel, or riprap shores to shores mimicking natural shores such as rocky and shingle shores etc.

The vegetation of artificial shores varies from natural lake-, river-, and seashore vegetation to planted lawns, shrubs, and trees. The vegetation of artificial shores is often more managed and meagre compared with comparable natural shores.

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, artificial shores resemble natural shores. The shore is constructed using natural materials similar to rocky, shingle, sandy etc. shores. The shore profile gradient is variable and is at least partially gentle. Versatile natural aquatic and shore plants typical for the shore type grow in clear zones on the shore. The immediate zone around the shore is mostly comprised of a permeable, unpaved surface, and the shore also has shelter trees or other sheltering vegetation.

In the best scenario, artificial shores offer versatile habitats for aquatic and shore communities, and artificial shores cannot be distinguished in practice from comparable natural shores. The shore zone communities can be fairly diverse, as various microhabitats form on the shores through fluctuations in water depth and water surface.

Assessment tables for condition: Artificial shores

	Aquatic and shore vegetation: 1) multispecied, 2) versatility (includes shore vegetation, helophytes, floating-leaved plants, and submerged plants, 3) native Finnish and/or European species community and/or non-invasive neo- and archaeophyte species, 4) melliferous plants	Shore structure	Condition of adjacent zone <i>Adjacent habitat: area that has an immediate effect on the site</i>
1	Four attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	Shore analogous to natural shores. Shore consists of natural materials analogous to natural shores (earth materials, grain size, grain size variation). Shore profile is mostly gentle and exhibits small-scale variation.	Shore zone and adjacent zone have abundant tall/large trees and/or other sheltering vegetation, and the share of permeable surface is great.
0.9			
0.8	Three attributes present.		
0.7			
0.6	Two attributes present. Single invasive aliens plant species may be present.		
0.5		Shore is comprised of natural materials analogous to a natural shore. Shore profile is steep and uniform.	Shore and adjacent zone have at least some tall or short sheltering vegetation and partially permeable surfaces.
0.4	One attribute present. Several populations of invasive alien species may be present.		
0.3		Shore is comprised of very uniform material that does not resemble natural shores (stone riprap etc.) Shore profile is mostly gentle and exhibits small-scale variation.	
0.2			
0.1	No attributes present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	Shore is comprised of very uniform material that does not resemble natural shores (stone riprap etc.) Shore profile is steep and uniform.	Shore and adjacent zone are completely void of vegetation, and the share of permeable surface is small.
0	Not a habitat type		

Picture 50. An artificial shore in Helsinki. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 51. An artificial shore in Töölönlahti park, Helsinki. Picture: Merete Kemppainen.

Artificial water basins

Description of habitat type

This habitat type includes artificial water basins in which the water does not remain naturally; rather, the water levels are regulated. Artificial water basins can be found, for example, in parks and playgrounds. Water can be run into and out of the basin, and, if necessary, the basin can be completely or mostly water-free. The bottom can consist of various earth materials such as gravels or rocks. The vegetation is either planted or naturally spread aquatic or shore vegetation.

This habitat type does not include concrete troughs, water jars, water fountains etc. that are completely vegetation free or that have constructed bottoms. Stormwater depressions and other basins from which water is not run in or out of are considered to belong to artificial wetlands (see Artificial wetlands) or artificial ponds (see Artificial ponds).

Description of ideal ecological condition

In ideal ecological condition, artificial water basins have water year-round and abundant versatile aquatic and shore vegetation. The site does not have any invasive plant species. The basin's shore zone has sheltering vegetation such as tall/large trees.

Artificial water basins generally support biodiversity moderately poorly compared with other habitat types of constructed environments. The temporary and constructed nature of the basins decreases their potential in terms of biodiversity. However, in the best scenario, artificial water basins do offer habitat to aquatic species and, for example, to invertebrates laying their eggs in the water. In the summertime, small water basins can be important watering holes for animals.

Assessment tables for condition: Artificial water basins

	Aquatic and shore vegetation: 1) multispecied, 2) versatility (includes shore vegetation, hel- ophytes, floating-leaved plants, and submerged plants	Permanence of water	Condition of adjacent zone <i>Adjacent habitat: area that has an immediate effect on the site</i>
1	Both attributes present. No invasive alien plant species present.	Site has water year-round.	Shore zone and adjacent zone have abundant tall/large trees and/or other sheltering vegetation, and the share of permeable surface is great.
0.9			
0.8			
0.7			
0.6			
0.5	One attribute present. Invasive alien plants may be present.	Site is dry occasionally, for example a few weeks during dry summers.	Shore and adjacent zone have at least some tall or short sheltering vegetation and a partially permeable surface.
0.4			
0.3			
0.2			
0.1	Neither attribute present. Area can be widely overgrown by invasive plant species.	Site has water only intermittently, for example after heavy rains or flooding.	Shore zone and adjacent zone is completely void of vegetation and share of permeable surface is small.
0	Not a habitat type		

Picture 52. An artificial pool in Helsinki. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 53. An artificial pool in Kotka. Picture: Anna Pursiainen.

Picture 54. A dry artificial pool in Tampere. Picture: Elisa Lähde.

Picture 55. A water basin in Skeppet, Tammissaari. Picture: Alli-Maiju Hurmola.

Artificial ponds and running waters

Artificial ponds and running waters are assessed using the assessment criteria for natural small waterbodies.

Artificial ponds: This habitat type comprises artificial ponds with natural hydrology unregulated water levels. The ponds have water year-round. The ecological condition of the habitat type is assessed using the assessment criteria of natural ponds (Jalkanen et al. 2026).

Artificial running waters: This habitat type comprises the channels of artificial or translocated running waters. These are not differentiated from natural running waters, and the ecological condition of artificial running waters is assessed using the assessment criteria of natural running waters (Jalkanen et al. 2026). As a baseline, the running waters of this habitat type have continuously flowing water. Seasonally dry stormwater channels etc. are assessed as artificial wetlands.

Picture 56: An artificial pond in Korppaanpuisto, Helsinki. Picture: Elisa Lähde.

References

Jalkanen, J., Nieminen, E., Ahola, A., Luoma, E., Pekkonen, M., Halme, P., Kotiaho, J. S. & Kujala, H. (2026) Defining ecologically realistic biodiversity offset multipliers with the Response-based Habitat Hectare Assessment of Biodiversity Gains (REHAB). *BiorXiv*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.64898/2026.01.26.701764>.

Kempainen, R. (2017) Perinnemaisemien inventointiohje [Inventory guide for Finnish traditional agricultural habitats]. *Varsinais-Suomen elinkeino-, liikenne- ja ympäristökeskuksen raportteja 25/2017*, pp. 94.

RAMS (2020) Viheralueiden kunnossapitoluokitus [Finnish management classification of green spaces]. *Viherympäristöliitto ry*, pp 67.